

Improvement of black soybean performances with application of bio-nano orthosilicic acid on acid dry land soil

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ABSTRACT

Soybean is one of the major food commodities in Indonesia, but the production of soybean itself is still low in the last five years. As an effort to fulfill the needs of domestic soybean, marginal land soil could be utilized for black soybean, however its challenge is generally infertile soils. One of marginal land soil that can be used is acid dry land (ADL) soil characterized by low organic matter content and pH value. The objective of this study was to determine the effect of application of bio-nano-silica in the form orthosilicic acid (OSA) in acid dry land soil on : (i) black soybean vegetative growth and (ii) black soybean yield. The research was conducted in Natar area, South Lampung, in July–October 2017, by using a randomized block design with three replicates. Bio-nano OSA was applied at 0, 2, 4, and 6 L/ha, whereas single N, P, and K fertilizers were given at 0, 50, 75, and 100% of recommended rate on a 100 m² plot size each, with control plot and farmer's standard practice plot (100% N, P, and K + 2ton/ha of organic matter). Bio-nano OSA was prepared from a 325-mesh quartz sand using acid base solution extraction method and contained 5% H₄SiO₄ with 18 nm particle size applied in combination with selected Si-solubilizing microorganism, i.e. *Aeromonas punctata*, *Burkholderia cenocepacia*, *B. vietnamiensis*, and *Aspergillus niger*. The results indicated that the application of bio-nano OSA at 4 L/ha was able to save NPK fertilizer dosages up to 50% fertilizer and improved both vegetative and yield performances of Detam-1 black soybean variety on Ultisols of Natar.

Keywords: acid dry land soil, bio-nano OSA, black soybean, silica-solubilizing microorganism

INTRODUCTION

Demand of black soybean, *Glycine soja* (L) merit increases steadily as a consequence of developing new soy sauce industries. However, the ben supply domestically is not sufficient yet due to low productivity of infertile land. Land

infertility are due to low efficiency in water and nutrients usages. Many efforts have been conducted to improve yield but unfortunately there were not successful. As an effort to fulfill the needs of domestic black soybeans was by exploiting marginal land soil. One of marginal land soil that can be used is those belong to acid dry land (ADL) soil.

Lampung is province with alarge area ofADLsoils that potential for food crops covering 98,234 ha (Ritung et al. 2015). Acid dry land soilsgenerally have low organic matter content and pH value. The cultivation of land can not be maximized because the mainproblem is aluminum toxicity and/or low availability of phosphorus (P) of the soil , as well as the drought stress (Diedrich et al. 2012; Cristancho andRestrepo 2014). In general, to overcome this problem ofsoybean cultivation in ADLsoilsis lime application to increase soil pH.The drought stress remains unsolved yet.

Many reports show that silica (Si) application to soil could relieve plant from the drought stress (Diedrich et al. 2012; Edward 2014). Therefore, the use of Si element, particularly in form of readily available such as ortho-silicic-acid (OSA) that could be considered as an alternative to resolve some problem inADL. Si can improveplantresistance against drought and reduce potentially aluminium toxicity (Ashraf andHarris 2013). The addition of Si to plants is believed the plants become more resistant to drought through leafcell biosilificationwhich increase the strength of the cell wall (Farooq et al. 2009).

Many Si fertilizer products are starting to be available in the market during the last few years with various quality that depend on total SiO₂ content which actually unavailable to plants. Currently there is anew Si fertilizer developed by the Indonesian Research Institute for Biotechnology and Bioindustry (IRIBB), i.e. bio-nano OSA, which combines the microbial and nanotechnological approach. This research was conducted to evaluate the effect of bio-nano OSA application combined by dosages of NPK fertilizers on black soybean vegetative growthand yield under ADL soils condition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location and design of experiment

This research was carried out in Natar Experimental Station, Assessment Institute for Agricultural Technology, South Lampung, Lampung, starting fromJuly until October 2017. Chemical characterisitics of Ultisols in experimental plot were pH 5.18,1.38% C-organic, 0.18%N-total, 0.009% P₂O₅, 0.002% K₂O, and 10.66 cmol/kg CEC. The experimentused a randomized block design with 17 treatments and 3 replicates (Table 1). The treatments were

consisting of bio-nano OSA and NPK fertilizer combinations in different dosages. Bio-nano OSA was applied at 0, 2, 4, and 6 L/ha, whereas NPK fertilizers were given at 0, 50, 75, and 100% equivalent to recommended dosages, each in a 100 m² plot size. Data obtained analyzed statistically with ANOVA and Duncan Multiple Range Test (Steel and Torrie 1980).

Table 1. Treatments of Bio-Nano OSA and NPK fertilizers.

Treatments	Treatment Codes
Blank (without fertilizer)	K1
100% NPK + 20 kg organic matter	K2
Bio-Nano OSA 2 L ha ⁻¹	B1
Bio-Nano OSA 4 L ha ⁻¹	B2
Bio-Nano OSA 6 L ha ⁻¹	B3
50% NPK	P1
75% NPK	P2
100% NPK	P3
50% NPK + 2 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹	P1B1
75% NPK + 2 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹	P2B1
100% NPK + 2 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹	P3B1
50% NPK + 4 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹	P1B2
75% NPK + 4 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹	P2B2
100% NPK + 4 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹	P3B2
50% NPK + 6 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹	P1B3
75% NPK + 6 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹	P2B3
100% NPK + 6 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹	P3B3

Fertilizer application and observation

Bio-nano OSA was prepared from a 325-mesh quartz sand using acid base solution extraction method and contained 5% H₄SiO₄ with 18 nm particle size applied in combination with selected Si-solubilizing microorganism, i.e. *Aeromonas punctata*, *Burkholderia cenocepacia*, *B. vietnamiensis*, and *Aspergillus niger* (Santi and Goenadi 2017). This experiment used a Detam-1 black soybean variety with planting space of 20 x 40 cm and two seeds per hole. Prior to application the seeds were coated with a commercial product containing non-symbiotic N-fixing and phosphate solubilizing bacteria, i.e. RhiPhosant (Goenadi and Santi 2009; Hafif and Santi 2016). Liming was performed prior to by applying 500 kg CaCO₃/ha equivalent to 1,500 kg dolomite. Application of NPK fertilizers were conducted 14 day after planting (DAP) with the rate of 100% NPK fertilizers was 75 kg Urea + 100 kg SP36 + 100 kg KCl per ha. Application of bio-nano OSA was performed 28 DAP by spraying the liquid formula after 100x dilution with water to the soil surface surrounding the plants. The parameters observed were selected vegetative and yield indicators,

i.e. (1) height of plant, (2) number of leaves, (3) number of productive branches, (4) number of pods, and (5) biomass of the plants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Black soybean vegetative growth

The effects of drought on soybean have been extensively reported, including morphological changes of the vegetative plant and the reduction in seed quantity and quality. Methods for assessing both quantitative and qualitative morphological parameters have been reported. In this research, the vegetative data of black soybean observed were the height of plants, number of leaves, and number of productive branches. The data show that the application of bio-nano OSA improved the vegetative growth of the plant compared to the 100% NPK treatment (Table 2), both as single application and in combination with reduced dosage of NPK fertilizer treatments particularly at 4 L ha⁻¹ dosage.

Table 2. Vegetative growth of black soybean in ADL soil.

Treatments	Height of Plants (cm)	Number of Leaves	Number of Productive Branch
Blank (without fertilizer) (K1)	23,9 ef ^{*)}	17,2 efg	2,7 bcde
100% NPK + 20 kg organic matter (K2)	25,3 def	19,2 cdef	2,6 bcde
Bio-Nano OSA 2 Lha ⁻¹ (B1)	26,6 bcde	19,5 abcdef	3,6 ab
Bio-Nano OSA 4 Lha ⁻¹ (B2)	25,5 cdef	19,3 bcdef	2,9 bcde
Bio-Nano OSA 6 Lha ⁻¹ (B3)	25,8 cdef	18,9 cdef	2,4 cde
50% NPK (P1)	24,2 def	16,7 fg	1,8 e
75% NPK (P2)	27,7 bc	21,0 abc	2,3 cde
100% NPK (P3)	22,9 f	14,9 g	1,9 de
50% NPK + 2 L Bio-Nano OSAha ⁻¹ (P1B1)	24,2 def	17,6 defg	2,5 cde
75% NPK + 2 L Bio-Nano OSAha ⁻¹ (P2B1)	23,8 ef	20,4 abcde	2,5 cde
100% NPK + 2 L Bio-Nano OSAha ⁻¹ (P3B1)	26,2 bcde	21,4 abc	2,6 bcde
50% NPK + 4 L Bio-Nano OSAha ⁻¹ (P1B2)	23,5 ef	19,9 abcde	3,2 abc
75% NPK + 4 L Bio-Nano OSAha ⁻¹ (P2B2)	36,0 a	21,9 abc	2,6 bcde
100% NPK + 4 L Bio-Nano OSAha ⁻¹ (P3B2)	25,4 cdef	20,8 abcd	3,0 bcd
50% NPK + 6 L Bio-Nano OSAha ⁻¹ (P1B3)	27,3 bcd	20,7 abcde	3,4 abc
75% NPK + 6 L Bio-Nano OSAha ⁻¹ (P2B3)	27,8 bc	22,9 ab	4,2 a
100% NPK + 6 L Bio-Nano OSAha ⁻¹ (P3B3)	29,2 b	23,2 a	3,3 abc

^{*)} Figures in the same column followed by the same letter(s) are not significantly different according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (P<0.05).

However, in general these results were considerably less than those vegetative performances of Detam-1 black soybean variety reported by others (Lumbantobing et al. 2013; Rasyid 2013). The reason for this evidence is suspected to be an intensive dry season during the experiment in which there were no rain at all in the period of August-October 2017 at experimental site.

However, it indicates that the Si application with or without NPK fertilizers promoted a better growth conforming that Si uptake by plants may improve the stomata opening during the drought stress as reported by Santi et al. (2018). This phenomenon may improve photosynthesis and nutrient uptake as well resulting in a more active growth of the plants during the drought season.

Black soybean yield

The parameter data of black soybean yield were collected in the number of pods and biomass of the plants. The results show that the application of bio-nano OSA was also able to give the best results, especially on the application dose of 4 L ha⁻¹ (Table 3).

Table 3. Black soybean yield in ADL soil.

Treatments	Number of Pods	Biomass of the plants (g)
Blank (without fertilizer) (K1)	30 e ⁾	9,055 h
100% NPK + 20 kg Organic Matter (K2)	33,5 Cd	10,23 fgh
Bio-Nano OSA 2 L ha ⁻¹ (B1)	30,5 E	9,495 gh
Bio-Nano OSA 4 L ha ⁻¹ (B2)	34,5 bc	13,13 cd
Bio-Nano OSA 6 L ha ⁻¹ (B3)	37,5 b	12,22 cdef
50% NPK (P1)	31,5 de	10,66 efgh
75% NPK (P2)	37 b	15,60 ab
100% NPK (P3)	41 a	12,71 cde
50% NPK + 2 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹ (P1B1)	35 bc	13,33 bc
75% NPK + 2 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹ (P2B1)	42 a	16,19 a
100% NPK + 2 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹ (P3B1)	42,5 a	10,77 defgh
50% NPK + 4 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹ (P1B2)	41,5 a	15,59 ab
75% NPK + 4 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹ (P2B2)	40,5 a	15,48 ab
100% NPK + 4 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹ (P3B2)	41 a	16,04 a
50% NPK + 6 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹ (P1B3)	37,5 b	11,61 cdefg
75% NPK + 6 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹ (P2B3)	41,5 a	10,84 defgh
100% NPK + 6 L Bio-Nano OSA ha ⁻¹ (P3B3)	40,5 a	12,61 cdef

⁾ Figures in the same column followed by the same letter(s) are not significantly different according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (P<0.05).

Moreover, the results also show that with the addition of bio-nano OSA can save chemical fertilizer up to 50%. Relationships between dosages of fertilizer N, P, and K fertilizers and the number of pods produced by black soybeans var. Detam-1 on each dosage of bio-nano OSA are significant i.e. R² = 0.94; 0.97; and 0.97, respectively (Figure 1).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 1. The relationship between NPK fertilizer dosages and number of pods of black soybean Detam-1 var. using 2(a), 4 (b), and 6 L ha⁻¹ (c) bio-nano OSA, respectively.

Meanwhile, the relationship between dosage of fertilizer N, P, and K and the plant biomass produced by black soybeans var. Detam-1 on each dosage of bio-nano OSA is also significant with somewhat lower values of determination coefficients i.e. $R^2 = 0,78$; $0,98$; and $0,81$, respectively (Figure 2). Both interaction relationships indicate that up to 4 L ha⁻¹ the higher dosages of

bio-nano OSA more closely related to dosages of NPK fertilizer. These evidences again show that Si play an important role in promoting the growth and yield performances of Detam-1 black soybean variety on soil in ADL environment.

Figure 2. The relationship between NPK fertilizer dosages and biomass of black soybean Detam-1 var. using 2(a), 4 (b), and 6 L ha⁻¹ (c) bio-nano OSA, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

The application of newly constructed formula of bio-nano OSA on an Ultisol soil under ADL environment promoted better growth and yield performances of Detam-1 black soybean variety. At 4 L ha⁻¹ dosage of bio-nano OSA, it was able to save NPK fertilizer dosages up to 50%. However, further study is needed to confirm these results, especially at other location and a wider application.

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